

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

DEVELOPMENT OF NEW TECHNOLOGIES FOR SAMPLING COTTON SEEDS BY THE COMBINED ASAU METHOD AND OBTAINING SEED MATERIAL

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the development of technologies for the production of quality sowing material, which is the main problem of cotton growing, which has a greater share in the agricultural sector, which is the basis of the economy of the republic.

For this purpose, a new technology for the production of sowing material was developed as a result of the selection of biologically mature yarns during the combined sorting of fibrous cotton yarns, as well as processing of these yarns by the proposed method, and two positive decisions were made by the Intellectual Property Agency.

In addition to the mentioned advantages of the proposed technology, the use of low-percentage starch solution, as well as absorbents with high absorption capacity (zeolite or bentonite) in the country to improve the quality of sowing material in the production of sowing material as a result of processing raw materials. indicates that it has indicators.

Keywords: fiber, cotton, yarn, combined, sorting, sowing material, production, technology.

Introduction. As a result of the greater weight of the agricultural sector in the country, the "Strategic Roadmap" of the country's economic development, adopted by the decree of President Ilham Aliyev on December 6, 2016, attaches great importance to the development of cotton growing. , performance increase caught. If the employment of the population working in the agricultural sector in the regions of the republic, the demand of light industry enterprises for cotton products, etc., then the relevance and priority of the field are no exception.

Along with its relevance, one of the main problems of cotton growing in our country is related to the need for high-quality seed material.

Currently, 60-65 kg of low-flow cotton fiber produced at the country's cotton gins cannot be sorted either by weight or volume in sorting devices or in various media (air, water jet, etc.) sprinkled with raisins. If we consider that hundreds of thousands of hectares of land are sown with willow in the republic, then this is a

big economic waste - during the heyday of work, a lot of labor is required to thin out seedlings and so on. clearly visible.

As a result of the research work carried out at the department of "Technical mechanics and graphics" of the ASAU, the general view is shown in figure 1, a device of the kirkir type with large economic, operational and environmental indicators (at the patent level) was created. satisfactory results have been developed, investigated and obtained.

The ASAU method for sorting bales of fibrous cotton is carried out in the following sequence: in the Kirkir centrifugal apparatus (Fig. 1), consisting of disks with an elastic coating (password) in contact with a low-percentage starch solution on the surface (fig. 1) and a vibrating vibrator In the sorter, interrelated processes on fibrous cotton stems are carried out by sorting the stems first by their mass, and then by taking the same or larger masses from them to obtain smaller ones.

Fig. 1.

General view of a Kirkira-type device for sorting bales of fibrous cotton by the combined "ASAU" method.

Figure 2. Technological scheme of the vibrating volume sorting device

Let's look at figure 2, the technological scheme of the volume sorter:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} M'_1 = M''_1 \\ M'_2 = M''_2 \\ M'_i = M''_i \end{array} \right. \text{ we see that.} \quad (1)$$

Here: $M'_1, M'_2 \dots M'_i \neq M''_1, M''_2 \dots M''_i$ respectively, the vibrating volume is the mass of the samples on and through the sorting plate of the sorting device. Also look at the sorting device,

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} V'_1 > V''_1 \\ V'_2 > V''_2 \\ \text{we see that} \\ V'_i > V''_i \end{array} \right. \quad (2)$$

Here: $V'_1, V'_2 \dots V'_i \neq V''_1, V''_2 \dots V''_i$ respectively, the vibrating volume is the volume of the samples on and through the sorting plate of the sorting device.

If we study systems (1) and (2) together, we get

$$\frac{M'_1}{V'_1} < \frac{M''_1}{V''_1} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{because } \rho = \frac{M}{V}, \quad (4)$$

Inequality (3) can be written as $\rho' < \rho''$. (5)

Here: ρ - is the density of the ridges..

From (1):

$$M'_i = M''_i \quad (6)$$

Also, if we look at Figure 3, we see that,

Figure 3. General view of cross-sections of cotton yarns of the same mass, different volumes, sorted by the combined method "ASAU": M'_i, V'_i and M''_i, V''_i ; -a) and passing-b) are the same mass and different volumes, the volume of which does not pass through the sorter, respectively.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} M'_i = M'_i \text{ (spare food item)} + m'_i \text{ (bark)} \\ M''_i = M''_i \text{ (spare food item)} + m''_i \text{ (bark)} \end{array} \right. \quad (7)$$

where m'_i (shell) and m''_i (shell) are the mass of the shell of the strings on and passing through the sorting plate of the sorting device, respectively, the vibrating volume.

(1) and(7):

m'_i (spare food item)+ m'_i (shell) = m''_i (spare food item)+ m''_i (shell) we can write

If we look at figure 2, we see that m'_i (shell) > m''_i (shell). (8)

Expression (9) leads to the conclusion that (8) is true

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} m'_1 < m''_1 \\ m'_2 < m''_2 \\ m'_i < m''_i \end{array} \right. \quad (10)$$

Here: $m'_1, m'_2 \dots m'_i$ and $m''_1, m''_2 \dots m''_i$, respectively and the mass of reserve nutrients.

Expression (10) allows us to conclude that in the proposed method, the same masses are first selected, and then smaller ones, in other words, having a supply of nutrients in the shell and the mass of the beginning of the embryo. seed material).

As a result of the application of the proposed ASAU method, a high-quality, vibro-vibrating volumetric sorting device (Fig. 2 b) and a relatively low-quality one, which is obtained from the use of a Kirk-shaped centrifugal type device in local cotton gins, seeds can be obtained (fig. 2 a).

Accurate sowing in modern pneumatic seeders is possible from a larger mass, as well as high-grained (fluid) seed material obtained as a result of sorting fibrous cotton stalks by the proposed method. With the help of the method, in addition to the above qualitative indicators of the seed material, it is possible to achieve greater economic efficiency by using a low-percentage starch solution to moisten the seeder discs (elastic material) A pickaxe-shaped centrifugal type of fibrous cotton seeds.

The proposed method for obtaining seed material from biologically mature fibrous cotton seeds sorted by the ASAU method is carried out in the following sequence.

As mentioned above, the essence of the proposed method for obtaining seed material from fibrous cotton stems is that the fibers are wrapped in their outer surfaces using previously known methods and devices [1...9], as well as sorted by weight. , the outer surface of starch treated with liquid starch is treated with a liquid fungicide - when it exits the apparatus in a wet state (fig. 4; 5), the absorbent (zeolite and bentonite) passes through the nozzle in the form of powder and settles on the surface of the absorbent cores. Absorbents that are able to absorb more than ten times their own liquid mass prevent the destruction of drought by drought, providing faster and simultaneous germination of seedlings. An absorbent hopper was used to improve the quality. in front of the fungicide-treated drum, the working width of which is equal to the width of the drum (fig. 5), and the axes of symmetry of the shafts are parallel to each other.

The problem is solved by rotating the working surfaces between their working surfaces moistened with fixed rubber and movable elastic material around the axis of symmetry of fibrous cotton threads, as well as the outer surfaces by the method of obtaining seed material from fibrous cotton threads, fibrous cotton swabs moistened with a liquid starch-fungicidal mixture are passed through a powdered absorbent nozzle at the end of the translational movement.

The essence of the method consists in sequential moistening and wrapping of seeds (accelerates germination), the approach of water-moist air to the seed coat (eliminates the negative effect of fungicides on seed germination), increasing the granularity of the starch solution. in the soil, the destruction of diseases on the seedling (ensuring the development of seedlings), the absorbent provides moisture to the outer surface of the seedling (providing water to the plant at a later stage of development).

In accordance with the soil and climatic conditions of the republic, the possibility of sowing seed material obtained in a wet state as a result of the application of the method proposed by us shows that it has great technological potential. When using the "Method of obtaining seed material from fibrous cotton stems", the quality of the seed material is significantly improved compared to the currently known methods used for this purpose, as a result of the implementation of the proposed interrelated processes in the sequence above. .

To improve the quality of reception, the movement is transmitted by a chain from the electric motor

to the drum shaft, and from there to the shafts of metering devices installed in the hopper and absorbent bunkers.

There are 15 additional containers in the unit to protect the environment and reuse excess absorbent.

The drums and hoppers of the electric motor are connected to the support 16. (fig. 4)

The technological scheme of the device for implementing the method of production of seed material from fibrous cotton threads is shown in figure -4;5

Figure-4 Technological scheme of the plant for the production of seed material from fibrous cotton threads sorted by the combined "ASAU" method

Fig. 5. View A-A from Fig. 4

Currently, theoretical and practical studies of the technical means developed by us in figure 6 and a model example in Figure 7 are being conducted to further increase the capabilities of these technologies.

Figure-6 Technological scheme of a pick-shaped sorting device

Fig. 7. Model of the plant for processing fibrous cotton fiber with starch solution.

Conclusion The use of the ADAU method for sorting cotton-fiber seedlings by the proposed combined method and various elements of the technology for obtaining seed material not only cotton-fiber seeds, but also seeds of other fibrous crops, other technical, vegetable seeds. it can also be used in the creation of machinery and equipment for sorting and production of seed material.

References

1. Dyachkov V.V., Kattakhodzhaev R. M. "The method of sorting cotton seeds and the device for its implementation" Auth svid. USSR No. 1695839. A 01C 1/00. VNIPI. Byul. No. 45. M.1991.7 p.
2. Babayev Sh.M. Determination of the living section of the window for grading granular materials Journal "Current Issues of Modern Science" No. 1(17) January 2018, St. Petersburg 5 p
3. Babayev Sh.M. Justification of the optimal parameters of the injector sprayer. Collection of scientific papers. Scientific and practical conference in the agro-industrial complex: Innovations, problems, development prospects. November 22 , 2019 Tver, pp.124-131.
4. Babayev Ş.M. Çeşitleyici Cihazının Gelişimi ve Metrolojik Araştırılması mekale Türk Dünyası Araştırmaları Uluslararası Bilimler Akademisi IX. Uluslararası Sempozyum Bildirileri (I cilt). Türkiye, Ankara, 2020, seh. 55-60.
5. Babayev Sh.M. Results of application of the modified tip of the sprayer sprayer in foliar processing of fodder crops. Agrotechnological Academy V.I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal University. News of agricultural science of Taurida. No.24 (187) 2020. D 01 10.37279/2413-1946, pp.50-66.
6. Babayev Sh.M. Results of tests of local technology of mechanization of plant protection. Zh. "Tractors and agricultural machinery" No. 11, 2011
7. Babayev Sh.M. Calculation of the parameters of the dosing device to intensify the process of regulating the concentration of the solution. IF RSCI Zh . "Izvestiya vuzov. Food Technology" No. 5-6 (December) 2014 Krasnodar, Moskovskaya str., 2, KubSTU
8. Babayev Sh.M. Determination of the living section of the window for sorting granular materials. Topical issues of modern science. Scientific journal. No. 1(17). Sanct Petersburg.2017. (The journal is posted on the website of the scientific electronic library eLiBRARY.RU)
9. Babayev Sh.M. Development and research of new technology and devices for mechanization of cotton seed etching and chemical plant protection of vegetable and berry crops in the conditions of Azerbaijan. Journal: Innovations in Agriculture. № 4 (25), 2017. Moscow, FGBNU Federal Scientific Agroengineering Center VIM. (The journal is included in the Russian Science Citation Index (RSCI)
10. Babayev Sh.M. Development and research of new technologies and equipment for cotton sorting. Ministry of Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Azerbaijan State University of Economics. UNEC. Faculty of Technology and Design. Prospects for the development of the food and textile industry in the country and tasks for the future. Materials of the II Republican Scientific and Practical Conference. April 25 , 2018 pp. 161-164
11. Babayev Sh.M. Theoretical study of a device for dosing bulk materials. Collection of scientific papers of the Azerbaijan Technical University. No. 2. Baku 2018.5 p.123.
12. Babayev Sh.M. Device for dosing bulk materials. State Committee for Standardization, Metrology and Patents of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The decision on the positive result of the re-examination. 2017 a 2017 0066 Baku.2018.5 p.
13. Babayev Sh.M. Determination of the living section of the window for sorting granular materials. Topical issues of modern science. Scientific journal g 1.No. 1(17). Saint Petersburg.2017. (The journal is published on the website of the scientific electronic library eLiBRARY.RU),pp. 27-32.
14. Babayev Sh.M. Development and research of new technology and devices for mechanization of cotton seed etching and chemical plant protection of vegetable and berry crops in the conditions of Azerbaijan. Journal: Innovations in Agriculture. № 4 (25), 2017. Moscow, FGBNU Federal Scientific Agroengineering Center VIM.(The journal is included

in the Russian Science Citation Index (RSCI).pp. 162-165.

15. Babayev Sh.M. Combined method of sorting fibrous cotton stems. State Committee for Standardization, Metrology and Patents of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The decision on the positive result of the re-examination. 2018 a 2018 0020 Baku. 19.02.2018.6p.

16. Babayev Sh.M. Investigation of technological characteristics of a device for dosing a solution. IF RSCI Zh. "Izvestiya vuzov. Food Technology" No.2-3 (December) 2015 Krasnodar, Moskovskaya str., 2, KubSTU

17. Babayev Sh.M. Development and investigation of the Combined "ASAU" Method the Production of Spray Material. Europäische Akademie der Naturwissenschaften (in Hannover) e. V.MATERIALS OF INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM EANW vol II (economic, technical, biological) Germany // hannover -2018

18. Babayev Sh.M. "AzETBMI" device for sorting of fibrous cotton stalks. State Agency for Standardization, Metrology and Patents of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Patent I 2003 0075. 6 p.

19. Babayev Sh.M. "Device for regulating the sowing rate of scattered materials." State Committee for Standardization, Metrology and Patents of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Patent. I 2010 0028, 11 p.

20. Babayev Sh.M. State Committee for Standardization, Metrology and Patents of the Republic of Azerbaijan "Method of sorting fibrous cotton in water". Patent. I 2014 0083, 6 p.

21. Babayev Sh.M. "Device for sorting grain seeds". State Committee for Standardization, Metrology and Patents of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Patent. I 2015 0082, 7 p.

22. Babayev Sh.M. "Device for sorting granular materials". Intellectual Property Agency of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Patent I 2019 0079, p 8.

23. Babayev Sh.M. "Device for dosing of granular materials". Intellectual Property Agency of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Patent I 2020 0039, p 8.

24. Babayev Sh.M. "Method of production of seed material from fibrous cotton stems. Intellectual Property Agency of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Patent I 2019 0148, p. 8